

Neutrino Masses, the Gravitational Coupling Constant and the Cosmological Constant

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Abstract

We predict the masses of the three neutrino mass eigenstates to be $m_1 = m_0$, $m_2 = 4m_0$ and $m_3 = 22m_0$ where $m_0 = 2.281 \text{ meV}/c^2$. We arrive at these predictions by applying two phenomenological postulates to neutrino oscillation data. First, we postulate that m_0 is the smallest quantum of mass and that the masses of all the massive elementary particles are positive integer multiples of m_0 . Second, we postulate that the dark energy — which drives the accelerated expansion of the universe — is represented by a cosmological constant Λ , or, equivalently, a vacuum energy with constant density $\rho_\Lambda = \alpha_g^4 \rho_P$, where $\alpha_g = \frac{m_0}{M_P}$ is the gravitational coupling constant, M_P is the Planck mass and ρ_P is the Planck density. We also predict the squared-mass-difference ratio $\frac{\Delta_{31}}{\Delta_{21}} = \frac{m_3^2 - m_1^2}{m_2^2 - m_1^2}$ to be exactly 32.2. We use neutrino oscillation data to predict the value of the cosmological constant Λ as well, in agreement with the $\nu\Lambda\text{CDM}$ model. In addition, we compute (i) the effective electron neutrino mass m_β , (ii) the upper bound on the effective Majorana mass of the electron neutrino $m_{\beta\beta}$ and (iii) the lower bounds on half-lives of various isotopes expected to undergo a neutrinoless double beta decay ($0\nu\beta\beta$). Finally, we introduce a new natural system of units in which both m_0 and ρ_Λ are set equal to unity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Experimenters have discovered three flavours of neutrinos: electron neutrino ν_e , muon neutrino ν_μ and tau neutrino ν_τ . [1–3] These neutrinos continuously change flavours, i.e. they transform into one another, for example, $\nu_e \rightleftharpoons \nu_\mu$. [4, 5] This phenomenon of neutrino oscillations conclusively demonstrates that neutrinos possess nonzero masses. Cosmological observations and neutrino experiments indicate that these masses lie in the sub-electronvolt range, making neutrinos the lightest known massive elementary particles. [6–8] Despite this progress, the absolute neutrino masses remain unknown.

In this work, we infer neutrino masses by introducing two postulates — one concerning the neutrinos themselves and the other concerning the dark energy responsible for the accelerated expansion of the universe.

In the first postulate, we propose a new analogy between mass and charge. We postulate

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that the masses of massive elementary particles are ‘quantized’ — just like their charges — and that these masses are positive integer multiples of the smallest neutrino mass eigenvalue. We then use this postulate to define a fundamental constant, the gravitational coupling constant α_g .

The second postulate adds a new dimension to the cosmological constant problem.[9] Quantum Field Theory (QFT) provides a natural explanation for the existence of the dark energy in the form of a constant vacuum energy. However, the observed value of the vacuum energy differs from the value expected in QFT by a factor of 10^{-123} . [10] This is the well-known cosmological constant problem. In the second postulate, we elevate this factor of 10^{-123} to the status of a fundamental constant by assuming that it is equal to the gravitational coupling constant raised to the power 4, i.e. $\alpha_g^4 \sim 10^{-123}$.

The rest of this article is organised as follows. We begin in section II with a brief overview of the 3ν mixing model of neutrino oscillations. In section III, we introduce the quantum of mass postulate (the QoM postulate) and define the gravitational coupling constant α_g . In section IV, we present the cosmological constant postulate (the CC postulate). We also discuss how the ongoing Hubble tension constrains our ability to make predictions using the cosmological data. In section V, we predict the neutrino mass spectrum and the cosmological constant using the neutrino oscillation data. We also calculate the effective electron neutrino mass m_β . In addition, we make predictions about the effective Majorana mass $m_{\beta\beta}$ of electron neutrino and half-lives of various isotopes expected to undergo a neutrinoless double beta decay ($0\nu\beta\beta$). In section VI, we construct a new natural system of units. Finally, in section VII, we discuss the implications and limitations of the proposed postulates and their predictions.

II. THE 3ν MODEL

The phenomenological three-neutrino mixing model (the 3ν model) provides a good fit to the data from neutrino oscillation experiments. In this model, each neutrino flavour eigenstate — ν_e, ν_μ and ν_τ — is an admixture of three mass eigenstates ν_1, ν_2 and ν_3 with corresponding mass eigenvalues m_1, m_2 and m_3 . These eigenstates are related by

$$|\nu_\alpha\rangle = \sum_{i=1}^3 U_{\alpha i}^* |\nu_i\rangle \quad (1)$$

where U is the neutrino mixing matrix.[11] If neutrinos are Majorana particles, then U depends on six independent parameters which are conveniently chosen to be three mixing angles $\theta_{12}, \theta_{13}, \theta_{23} \in [0, \frac{\pi}{2}]$ and three phases $\delta, \eta_1, \eta_2 \in [0, 2\pi]$, so that

$$U = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_{23} & s_{23} \\ 0 & -s_{23} & c_{23} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{13} & 0 & s_{13} e^{-i\delta} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -s_{13} e^{i\delta} & 0 & c_{13} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{12} & s_{12} & 0 \\ -s_{12} & c_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} e^{i\eta_1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{i\eta_2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where $s_{ij} = \sin \theta_{ij}$ and $c_{ij} = \cos \theta_{ij}$.

If neutrinos are Dirac particles, then the two Majorana phases η_i can be absorbed into the neutrino states and then U is a function of the remaining four parameters,

$$U = \begin{pmatrix} c_{12} c_{13} & s_{12} c_{13} & s_{13} e^{-i\delta} \\ -s_{12} c_{23} - c_{12} s_{23} s_{13} e^{i\delta} & c_{12} c_{23} - s_{12} s_{23} s_{13} e^{i\delta} & s_{23} c_{13} \\ s_{12} s_{23} - c_{12} c_{23} s_{13} e^{i\delta} & -c_{12} s_{23} - s_{12} c_{23} s_{13} e^{i\delta} & c_{23} c_{13} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Applying the 3ν model to the neutrino oscillation data yields best-fit values of these four parameters — the three mixing angles θ_{ij} and the CP phase δ — as well as the squared mass differences,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{21} &= m_2^2 - m_1^2 \\ \Delta_{31} &= m_3^2 - m_1^2 \\ \Delta_{32} &= m_3^2 - m_2^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

We cannot determine either the Majorana phases η_i or the absolute neutrino masses m_i from the oscillation data. Even the ordering of these masses is unknown. There are two possible mass orderings:

- i Normal Ordering (NO): $m_1 < m_2 < m_3$.
- ii Inverted Ordering (IO): $m_3 < m_1 < m_2$.

In Table I, we list the best-fit values and 3σ ranges of the oscillation parameters relevant to this work for both orderings as reported by NuFIT 6.0 (IC24 with SK atmospheric data).[7] We adopt the NuFIT 6.0 dataset for definiteness; however, using the other recent global analysis by Capozzi et al (2020)[12] does not materially affect our conclusions.

Since Δ_{21}, Δ_{31} and Δ_{32} are nonzero, the heavier two masses (m_2 and m_3 for NO, m_1 and m_2 for IO) are nonzero. It remains unknown whether the lightest neutrino mass is nonzero.

NuFIT 6.0 (IC24 + SK atmospheric)	Best Fit	3σ Range	Ordering
Δ_{21} $(\text{meV}/c^2)^2$	74.9	$69.2 \rightarrow 80.5$	Both
Δ_{31} $(\text{meV}/c^2)^2$	2513	$2451 \rightarrow 2578$	Normal
Δ_{32} $(\text{meV}/c^2)^2$	-2484	$-2547 \rightarrow -2421$	Inverted
$\sin^2 \theta_{12}$	0.308	$0.275 \rightarrow 0.345$	Normal
$\sin^2 \theta_{13}$	0.02215	$0.02030 \rightarrow 0.02388$	Normal
δ ($^\circ$)	212	$124 \rightarrow 364$	Normal

TABLE I: The best-fit values and 3σ ranges of the neutrino oscillation parameters (needed in this work) from NuFIT 6.0 (IC24 with SK atmospheric data).

For later convenience, we denote the lightest neutrino mass by m_0 . Then, for NO, $m_1 = m_0$ whereas, for IO, $m_3 = m_0$.

III. QUANTUM OF MASS AND GRAVITATIONAL COUPLING CONSTANT

All elementary particles possess constant charges. Moreover, electric charge is quantized; the charge of any particle is an integer multiple of $e_0 = \frac{e}{3}$, the charge of the down antiquark, where e is the charge of a proton. We therefore identify e_0 as the ‘smallest quantum of charge’. The charge q of a particle is then given by $q = N_q e_0$ for some fixed integer N_q .

All elementary particles also possess constant masses. However, unlike electric charge, it remains unknown whether mass is quantized in an analogous manner. In this work, we propose that such a quantization exists. We assume that there exists a ‘smallest quantum of mass’ and that the masses of massive elementary particles are positive integer multiples of it. Since neutrinos are the lightest known massive elementary particles, they provide a

natural candidate for this smallest quantum of mass.

A. Quantum of Mass Postulate

We postulate the following:

- I m_0 , the mass of the lightest neutrino mass eigenstate, is nonzero.
- II m_0 is the smallest quantum of mass.
- III The mass eigenvalues of all the massive elementary particles — leptons, quarks, W and Z bosons and the Higgs boson — are positive integer multiples of m_0 .

We refer to this postulate as the quantum of mass postulate (the QoM postulate).

Note that the QoM postulate does not predict numerical values of masses of the elementary particles. For example, the postulate asserts that the mass of an electron is $m_e = N_e m_0$ for some fixed natural number N_e . However, it does not determine N_e and therefore, m_e . These masses need to be measured experimentally. In section V, we determine the neutrino masses using experimentally measured neutrino oscillation parameters.

B. Gravitational Coupling Constant

The dimensionless gravitational coupling constant is defined as[13],

$$\alpha_g = \frac{m_p}{M_P} \tag{5}$$

where m_p is the mass of an elementary particle like electron and $M_P = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c}{G}}$ is Planck mass.¹ Different choices of m_p lead to different definitions of α_g . In [13], the mass of a proton was used for m_p ; however, an electron was also acceptable. And in [14], the mass of an electron was used, although any other elementary particle would have served equally well. Since the QoM postulate accords a special status to the mass m_0 , we choose $m_p = m_0$. We therefore define

$$\alpha_g = \frac{m_0}{M_P} \tag{6}$$

¹ This definition is the ‘square root’ of the definition used in [13].

This relation between α_g and m_0 is analogous to the relationship between the fine-structure constant α and proton charge e

$$\sqrt{\alpha} = \frac{e}{Q_P} \quad (7)$$

where $Q_P = \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\hbar}{\mu_0 c}} = \sqrt{4\pi\epsilon_0\hbar c}$ is the Planck charge. We make this analogy more obvious by defining the electromagnetic coupling constant α_e as

$$\alpha_e = \frac{e_0}{Q_P} = \frac{\sqrt{\alpha}}{3} \quad (8)$$

Like α_e (or, α), we regard α_g as a fundamental constant of nature. It plays a central role in linking neutrinos and dark energy.

IV. COSMOLOGICAL CONSTANT

The origin and composition of dark energy remain unknown. The simplest phenomenological model of evolution of the universe, the Λ CDM model, assumes that the dark energy is represented by a cosmological constant Λ . We can interpret this cosmological constant as a vacuum energy with constant density ρ_Λ , where[10]

$$\rho_\Lambda c^2 = \frac{c^4}{8\pi G} \Lambda \quad (9)$$

If the present-day observed values of the Hubble constant and the vacuum energy density parameter are H_0 and Ω_Λ , then[10]

$$\rho_\Lambda = \frac{3}{8\pi G} \Omega_\Lambda H_0^2 \approx \Omega_\Lambda h^2 \times 1.8783 \times 10^{-26} \text{ kg/m}^3 \quad (10)$$

where $h = \frac{H_0}{100 \text{ km/s/Mpc}}$ is the reduced Hubble constant.

A. Cosmological Constant Postulate

In this work, we postulate a simple relationship between the vacuum energy density ρ_Λ and the gravitational coupling constant α_g . As a fundamental constant of nature, α_g sets the scale of the smallest quantum of mass m_0 via definition (6). We now propose that α_g also sets the scale of dark energy. Specifically, we postulate that the vacuum energy density is given by,

$$\rho_\Lambda = \alpha_g^4 \rho_P \quad (11)$$

where $\rho_P = \frac{c^5}{\hbar G^2}$ is the Planck density. We name this postulate the cosmological constant postulate (the CC postulate). And we refer to both the QoM and the CC postulates together as the postulates regarding the gravitational coupling constant or the GCC postulates in short.

An immediate consequence of the CC postulate is that the vacuum energy density is proportional to the fourth power of the lightest neutrino mass. Substituting the definition (6) in the postulate (11), we get,

$$\rho_\Lambda = \frac{c^3}{\hbar^3} m_0^4 \quad (12)$$

This kind of a relationship between the vacuum energy and the neutrino mass has been studied in the past and has sparked new ideas.[15–17] In our case, this relation is equivalent to the CC postulate.

The cosmological constant also shares similar relationship with m_0 . Using Eqs. (9), (11) and (12), we obtain,

$$\Lambda = \frac{8\pi}{L_P^2} \alpha_g^4 = \frac{8\pi G c}{\hbar^3} m_0^4 \quad (13)$$

where $L_P = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^3}}$ is the Planck length.

Since the GCC postulates are phenomenological, their justification rests entirely on their predictive power. We can predict the value of m_0 by first solving Eqs. (10) and (12) to get,

$$m_0 = \sqrt[4]{\frac{3\hbar^3}{8\pi G c^3} \Omega_\Lambda H_0^2} \approx 3 \sqrt[4]{\Omega_\Lambda h^2} \text{meV}/c^2 \quad (14)$$

and then substituting the value of $\Omega_\Lambda h^2$ obtained from cosmological observations. However, the ongoing Hubble tension complicates this approach.

B. Hubble Tension

Planck 2018 data provide the most precise value of $\Omega_\Lambda h^2$. [18] For the $\nu\Lambda\text{CDM}$ model², it reports $h = 0.6710_{-0.0067}^{+0.0120}$, $\Omega_b h^2 = 0.02236(15)$ and $\Omega_c h^2 = 0.1201(13)$ so that $\Omega_\Lambda h^2 = 0.3078_{-0.0104}^{+0.0177}$. A combined analysis of Planck, ACT and DESI data yields $h = 0.6836(29)$ and $\Omega_m = 0.3009(37)$ for the $\nu\Lambda\text{CDM}$ model so that $\Omega_\Lambda h^2 = 0.3267(45)$. [6] However, these values of h reported by Planck and DESI Collaborations differ significantly from the model independent, direct measurements of h obtained by late-time probes using distance ladders.

For example, Breuval et al[19] report $h = 0.7317(86)$. This disagreement in the measured values of h is known as the Hubble tension.

A resolution of this tension in favour of higher values of h would significantly shift the inferred value of $\Omega_\Lambda h^2$ and could potentially require modifications of the Λ CDM model itself. For this reason, we do not use cosmological measurements of $\Omega_\Lambda h^2$ to determine neutrino masses. Instead, in the next section we use neutrino oscillation data to infer the value of $\Omega_\Lambda h^2$. The only restriction we place on $\Omega_\Lambda h^2$ is that it lies in the interval $[0.2, 0.5]$. This interval includes the Planck and the DESI values of $\Omega_\Lambda h^2$ mentioned above and is large enough to encompass any possible future modifications of it.

V. THE PREDICTIONS

The QoM postulate requires that each of m_1, m_2 and m_3 be a positive integer multiple of m_0 . We therefore write

$$\begin{aligned} m_1 &= N_1 m_0 \\ m_2 &= N_2 m_0 \\ m_3 &= N_3 m_0 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

where N_1, N_2 and N_3 are natural numbers. Substituting Eqs. (14) and (15) into the definitions of the squared mass differences in Eqs. (4) we get,

$$\Delta_{21} = (N_2^2 - N_1^2) m_0^2 \approx 9 (N_2^2 - N_1^2) \sqrt{\Omega_\Lambda h^2} (\text{meV}/c^2)^2 \tag{16}$$

$$\Delta_{31} = (N_3^2 - N_1^2) m_0^2 \approx 9 (N_3^2 - N_1^2) \sqrt{\Omega_\Lambda h^2} (\text{meV}/c^2)^2 \tag{17}$$

$$\Delta_{32} = (N_3^2 - N_2^2) m_0^2 \approx 9 (N_3^2 - N_2^2) \sqrt{\Omega_\Lambda h^2} (\text{meV}/c^2)^2 \tag{18}$$

Exactly one of the natural numbers N_1, N_2 and N_3 must equal unity, depending on the neutrino mass ordering. To determine the possible values of the remaining natural numbers we use the 3σ ranges of $\Delta_{21}, \Delta_{31}, \Delta_{32}$ together with the extended range $[0.2, 0.5]$ for $\Omega_\Lambda h^2$ into Eqs. (16), (17) and (18). Because the neutrino mass ordering remains experimentally unresolved, we do this for both the normal and inverted ordering separately, beginning with the inverted ordering.

² We consider the $\nu\Lambda$ CDM (Λ CDM + $\sum m_i$) model instead of the Λ CDM model because in this model, the sum of the neutrino masses $\sum m_i$ is allowed to vary.

A. Inverted Ordering (IO)

Under inverted ordering, ν_3 is the lightest mass eigenstate. Therefore $m_3 = m_0$, $1 = N_3 < N_1 < N_2$ and Eq. (18) becomes,

$$\Delta_{32} \approx 9 (1 - N_2^2) \sqrt{(\Omega_\Lambda h^2)} (\text{meV}/c^2)^2 \quad (19)$$

If we apply the constraint $\Omega_\Lambda h^2 \in [0.2, 0.5]$ to Eqs. (16) and (19), then, for the 3σ ranges of Δ_{21} and Δ_{32} we obtain the following restrictions on N_1 and N_2 ,

$$\begin{aligned} N_2^2 - N_1^2 &\in [10.9, 20.0] \\ &\& N_2 \in [19.53, 25.18] \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

No pair of natural numbers N_1 and $N_2 (> N_1)$ satisfy these restrictions simultaneously. We therefore conclude that, within the constraint $\Omega_\Lambda h^2 \in [0.2, 0.5]$, the GCC postulates, when applied to the neutrino oscillation data, are incompatible with the inverted mass ordering. This conclusion is well supported by experimental data, which shows a preference for normal ordering.[7]

B. Normal Ordering (NO)

Under normal ordering, ν_1 is the lightest mass eigenstate. Therefore $m_1 = m_0$, $1 = N_1 < N_2 < N_3$ and Eqs. (16) and (17) become,

$$\Delta_{21} = (N_2^2 - 1) m_0^2 \approx 9 (N_2^2 - 1) \sqrt{(\Omega_\Lambda h^2)} (\text{meV}/c^2)^2 \quad (21)$$

$$\Delta_{31} = (N_3^2 - 1) m_0^2 \approx 9 (N_3^2 - 1) \sqrt{(\Omega_\Lambda h^2)} (\text{meV}/c^2)^2 \quad (22)$$

If we apply the constraint $\Omega_\Lambda h^2 \in [0.2, 0.5]$ to Eq. (21), then, for the 3σ range of Δ_{21} , we obtain the following restriction on N_2 ,

$$\begin{aligned} N_2 &\in [3.45, 4.58] \\ \therefore N_2 &= 4 \end{aligned}$$

Eq. (21) then simplifies to

$$\Delta_{21} = 15m_0^2 \approx 135 \sqrt{(\Omega_\Lambda h^2)} (\text{meV}/c^2)^2 \quad (23)$$

Next, dividing Eq. (22) by Eq. (23) we get

$$\frac{\Delta_{31}}{\Delta_{21}} = \frac{(N_3^2 - 1)}{15} \quad (24)$$

Applying the 3σ ranges of Δ_{21} and Δ_{31} , we obtain the following restriction on N_3 ,

$$\begin{aligned} N_3 &\in [21.4, 23.7] \\ \therefore N_3 &= 22 \text{ or } 23 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, within the constraint $\Omega_\Lambda h^2 \in [0.2, 0.5]$, the GCC postulates, when applied to the neutrino oscillation data, predict that the neutrino masses obey normal mass ordering with,

$$\begin{aligned} m_1 &= m_0 \\ m_2 &= 4m_0 \\ m_3 &= 22m_0 \text{ or } 23m_0 \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Substituting the values of N_3 in Eq. (24) we get,

$$\frac{\Delta_{31}}{\Delta_{21}} = 32.2 \text{ or } 35.2 \quad (26)$$

This is an exact prediction that is directly testable through the neutrino oscillation experiments.

We cannot choose between the two possible values of N_3 with the current level of precision of the parameters Δ_{21} and Δ_{31} . We need more precise measurements. In NuFIT 6.0, the 3σ relative precision is 15% for Δ_{21} and 6% for Δ_{31} . The ongoing JUNO experiment will measure these parameters with better precision ($< 1\%$, [20]) corresponding to a 3σ relative precision of $< 6\%$ which may resolve this ambiguity.

We determine the value of m_0 by substituting the value of Δ_{31} into Eq. (22) (rather than using Eq. (23)) because Δ_{31} is known with greater precision. With the value of m_0 thus obtained, we compute the neutrino masses and their sum $\sum m_i$, the gravitational coupling constant $\alpha_g, \Omega_\Lambda h^2$, the vacuum energy density ρ_Λ and the cosmological constant Λ using Eqs. (25), (6), (14), (12) and (13). Table II lists the resulting best-fit values and 3σ ranges for both $N_3 = 22$ and $N_3 = 23$. The predicted sum of the three neutrino masses is consistent with the cosmological constraint of $\sum m_i < 64.2 \text{ meV}/c^2$ for the $\nu\Lambda\text{CDM}$ model.[6]

	Formula	$N_3 = 22$		$N_3 = 23$	
		Best Fit	3σ Range	Best Fit	3σ Range
$\frac{\Delta_{31}}{\Delta_{21}}$	$\frac{N_3^2 - 1}{4^2 - 1}$	32.2	-	35.2	-
$m_1 = m_0$ (meV/c ²)	$\sqrt{\frac{\Delta_{31}}{N_3^2 - 1}}$	2.281	2.253 → 2.310	2.182	2.155 → 2.210
m_2 (meV/c ²)	$4m_0$	9.124	9.011 → 9.241	8.726	8.618 → 8.839
m_3 (meV/c ²)	$N_3 m_0$	50.18	49.56 → 50.83	50.18	49.55 → 50.82
$\sum m_i$ (meV/c ²)	$(N_3 + 4 + 1) m_0$	61.59	60.82 → 62.38	61.09	60.33 → 61.87
α_g ($\times 10^{-31}$)	$\frac{m_0}{M_P}$	1.868	1.845 → 1.892	1.787	1.765 → 1.810
$\Omega_\Lambda h^2$	$\left(\frac{m_0}{3 \times 10^{-3}}\right)^4$	0.3344	0.3181 → 0.3519	0.2798	0.2662 → 0.2945
ρ_Λ ($\times 10^{-27}$ kg/m ³)	$\alpha_g^4 \rho_P$	6.281	5.975 → 6.610	5.256	5.000 → 5.531
Λ ($\times 10^{-52}$ m ⁻²)	$\alpha_g^4 \frac{8\pi}{L_P^2}$	1.172	1.115 → 1.234	0.9809	0.9331 → 1.032
m_β (meV/c ²)	$\sqrt{\sum U_{ei} ^2 m_i^2}$	9.19	8.68 → 9.69	9.05	8.55 → 9.55

TABLE II: Predicted values and 3σ ranges (for both $N_3 = 22$ and $N_3 = 23$) of $\frac{\Delta_{31}}{\Delta_{21}}$ (Eq. 26), neutrino mass eigenvalues m_1 (Eq. 22), m_2 and m_3 (Eqs. 25), sum of neutrino masses, gravitational coupling constant α_g (Eq. 6), $\Omega_\Lambda h^2$ (Eq. 14), vacuum energy density ρ_Λ (Eq. 12), the cosmological constant Λ (Eq. 13) and effective electron neutrino mass m_β (Eq. 28). Predictions for $\frac{\Delta_{31}}{\Delta_{21}}$ are exact. For rest of the predictions we use the best-fit values and 3σ ranges of Δ_{31} , $\sin^2 \theta_{12}$ and $\sin^2 \theta_{13}$ from table I. M_P is Planck mass, ρ_P is Planck density and L_P is Planck length.

1. β -Decay

β -decay allows us to directly measure the effective electron neutrino mass m_β using the principle of conservation of energy momentum. This mass is given by[11],

$$m_\beta = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^3 |U_{ei}|^2 m_i^2} \quad (27)$$

m_β is the same for both Dirac and Majorana neutrinos as only the magnitudes of the components of U enter the equation. Substituting Eqs. (3) and (25) in Eq. (27), we get

$$m_\beta = m_0 \sqrt{(N_3^2 - 1) s_{13}^2 + 15 s_{12}^2 (1 - s_{13}^2) + 1} \quad (28)$$

In the last row of table II, we list the best-fit values and 3σ ranges of m_β for both $N_3 = 22$ and $N_3 = 23$ calculated by substituting the best-fit values and 3σ ranges of m_0, s_{12} and s_{13} in Eq. (28). These predictions are well below the current upper limit of $m_\beta < 450 \text{ meV}/c^2$ set by KATRIN[8]. They are also below KATRIN's estimated sensitivity limit of about $300 \text{ meV}/c^2$.

2. Neutrinoless Double Beta Decay ($0\nu\beta\beta$)

Multiple experiments are searching for the first evidence of a neutrinoless double beta ($0\nu\beta\beta$) decay, $(A, Z) \longrightarrow (A, Z + 2) + e^- + e^-$. [11] Observation of a $0\nu\beta\beta$ decay will conclusively establish that neutrinos are Majorana particles. The corresponding decay half-life $T_{1/2}$ is related to the effective Majorana mass $m_{\beta\beta}$ of electron neutrino by,

$$T_{1/2} m_{\beta\beta}^2 = K \quad (29)$$

where the constant K is different for different isotopes undergoing the decay and

$$m_{\beta\beta} = \left| \sum_{i=1}^3 U_{ei}^2 m_i \right| \quad (30)$$

Substituting from Eqs. (2) and (25) and simplifying we get,

$$m_{\beta\beta} = m_0 \left| (1 - s_{12}^2) (1 - s_{13}^2) + 4 s_{12}^2 (1 - s_{13}^2) e^{2i(\eta_2 - \eta_1)} + N_3 s_{13}^2 e^{-2i(\delta + \eta_1)} \right| \quad (31)$$

Since the Majorana phases are unknown, we cannot predict $m_{\beta\beta}$ using this equation. Instead, we calculate the allowed range of $m_{\beta\beta}$ for $\eta_i \in [0, 2\pi]$ using 3σ ranges of m_0, s_{12}, s_{13}

and δ . We obtain $m_{\beta\beta} \leq 5.80 \text{ meV}/c^2$ for $N_3 = 22$ and $m_{\beta\beta} \leq 5.60 \text{ meV}/c^2$ for $N_3 = 23$. The lower bound of $m_{\beta\beta}$ is close to zero. Using these upper bounds, we infer lower bounds on the half-lives of various isotopes expected to undergo neutrinoless double beta decay. Table III summarizes these predictions alongside current experimental limits. The spread in the values of these lower bounds on the half-lives is due to uncertainties in the value of the constant K .

Isotope	Experiment	$0\nu\beta\beta$ Half-Life ($\times 10^{27}$ years)		
		Current Limit	Prediction	
			$N_3 = 22$ $m_{\beta\beta} \leq 5.80 \text{ meV}/c^2$	$N_3 = 23$ $m_{\beta\beta} \leq 5.60 \text{ meV}/c^2$
^{48}Ca	ELEGANT-VI[21]	$> 5.8 \times 10^{-5}$	$\geq 21 - 830$	$\geq 23 - 890$
^{76}Ge	GERDA[22]	> 0.18	$\geq 33 - 170$	$\geq 36 - 190$
^{82}Se	CUPID-0[23]	$> 4.6 \times 10^{-3}$	$\geq 9.4 - 41$	$\geq 10 - 44$
^{96}Zr	NEMO-3[24]	$> 9.2 \times 10^{-6}$	$\geq 14 - 100$	$\geq 15 - 110$
^{100}Mo	CUPID-Mo[25]	$> 1.8 \times 10^{-3}$	$\geq 4.2 - 13$	$\geq 4.5 - 14$
^{116}Cd	Aurora[26]	$> 2.2 \times 10^{-4}$	$\geq 6.5 - 19$	$\geq 7.0 - 20$
^{130}Te	CUORE[27]	$> 3.5 \times 10^{-2}$	$\geq 5.1 - 65$	$\geq 5.5 - 70$
^{136}Xe	KamLAND-Zen[28]	> 0.38	$\geq 8.8 - 170$	$\geq 9.5 - 180$
^{150}Nd	NEMO-3[29]	$> 2.0 \times 10^{-5}$	$\geq 1.5 - 17$	$\geq 1.6 - 18$

TABLE III: Predicted lower bounds on half-lives of various isotopes expected to undergo a neutrinoless double beta decay ($0\nu\beta\beta$) for both $N_3 = 22$ and $N_3 = 23$. Current experimental lower bounds on these half-lives are also listed.

VI. UNITS OF NATURE

A system of units defined entirely in terms of fundamental constants of nature is called a natural system of units. For example, Planck units are natural units as they are defined by setting $c = \hbar = G = k_B = 1$. [30] The special status accorded to the smallest quantum of mass m_0 and the vacuum energy density ρ_Λ by the GCC postulates allows us to construct a new natural system of units in which these quantities have unit magnitude. We define the

new system of units by setting,

$$m_0 = \rho_\Lambda = \hbar = e_0 = 1 \quad (32)$$

In this system,

$$\begin{aligned} c &= 1, & G &= \frac{\Lambda}{8\pi} = \alpha_g^2, \\ e &= 3, & \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} &= \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} = \alpha_e^2 \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

We define the unit of length in this system to be

$$l_0 = \sqrt[3]{\frac{m_0}{\rho_\Lambda}} \quad (34)$$

Using Eq. (12), we find that it is equal to the reduced Compton wavelength of m_0 ,

$$l_0 = \frac{\hbar}{m_0 c} \quad (35)$$

And we define the corresponding unit of time to be

$$t_0 = \frac{l_0}{c} = \frac{\hbar}{m_0 c^2} \quad (36)$$

As an illustrative example, the Coulomb force between two charges q_1 and q_2 separated by a distance r takes a simple form in the new system of units,

$$F_e = \alpha_e^2 \frac{q_1 q_2}{r^2} \quad (37)$$

where, q_1 and q_2 are integers. Similarly, the Newtonian gravitational force between two masses M_1 and M_2 separated by a distance r takes the form

$$F_g = \alpha_g^2 \frac{M_1 M_2}{r^2} \quad (38)$$

Next, consider the Einstein-Dirac-Maxwell action in SI units,

$$\begin{aligned} S &= \frac{c^3}{16\pi G} \int \sqrt{|g|} (R(g) - 2\Lambda) d^4x \\ &+ \frac{1}{c} \int \sqrt{|g|} \bar{\psi} (i \hbar c \gamma^\mu \nabla_\mu - c q \gamma^\mu A_\mu - m c^2) \psi d^4x \\ &- \frac{1}{4\mu_0 c} \int \sqrt{|g|} g^{\alpha\beta} g^{\gamma\mu} F_{\alpha\gamma} F_{\beta\mu} d^4x \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

In the new system of units, it becomes,

$$\begin{aligned} S &= \frac{1}{16\pi\alpha_g^2} \int \sqrt{|g|} (R(g) - 16\pi\alpha_g^2) d^4x \\ &+ \int \sqrt{|g|} \bar{\psi} (i \gamma^\mu \nabla_\mu - q \gamma^\mu A_\mu - m) \psi d^4x \\ &- \frac{1}{16\pi\alpha_e^2} \int \sqrt{|g|} g^{\alpha\beta} g^{\gamma\mu} F_{\alpha\gamma} F_{\beta\mu} d^4x \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

Here, the charge q of the elementary fermion is an integer and its mass m is a natural number.

VII. REMARKS

The CC postulate requires that dark energy is represented by a cosmological constant. Therefore the Λ CDM model and its extensions like $\text{o}\Lambda\text{CDM}$ ($\Lambda\text{CDM} + \Omega_K$) and $\nu\Lambda\text{CDM}$ are compatible with the CC postulate. In contrast, models involving dynamical dark energy — such as $w\text{CDM}$, $w_0w_a\text{CDM}$, quintessence and chameleon — are incompatible.

A. Vacuum Energy and Oscillation Parameters

Figure 1 illustrates the values of $\Omega_\Lambda h^2$ inferred from cosmological as well as neutrino oscillation data. The bottom three plots depict the best-fit values and 3σ ranges of $\Omega_\Lambda h^2$ calculated using neutrino oscillation data. We observe that the 3σ range $\Omega_\Lambda h^2 \in [0.263, 0.356]$ obtained from Eq. (23) using the 3σ range of Δ_{21} is large enough to encompass the 3σ ranges $\Omega_\Lambda h^2 \in [0.3181, 0.3519]$ for $N_3 = 22$ and $\Omega_\Lambda h^2 \in [0.2662, 0.2945]$ for $N_3 = 23$ obtained from Eq. (22) using the 3σ range of Δ_{31} . This explains why we cannot choose between the two possible values of N_3 using the neutrino oscillation data alone.

Cosmological data, however, show a preference for $N_3 = 22$ as can be seen from the top two plots in the figure. In particular, the value $\Omega_\Lambda h^2 = 0.3344$ predicted for $N_3 = 22$ lies closer to the DESI value $\Omega_\Lambda h^2 = 0.3267$ at 1.704σ whereas the value $\Omega_\Lambda h^2 = 0.2798$ predicted for $N_3 = 23$ deviated by 10.47σ .

The GCC postulates therefore impose a strong correlation between the 3ν model and the $\nu\Lambda\text{CDM}$ model when we choose $N_2 = 4$ and $N_3 = 22$. In particular, using $\Delta_{21} = 74.9 (\text{meV}/c^2)^2$ in Eq. (23) yields $\Omega_\Lambda h^2 = 0.308$ for $N_2 = 4$, consistent with both Planck 2018 and DESI results for the $\nu\Lambda\text{CDM}$ model. For any other value of N_2 , $\Omega_\Lambda h^2$ is either too small (0.120 for $N_2 = 5$) or too large (1.08 for $N_2 = 3$) as compared to the observed values.

FIG. 1: Whisker plots of $\Omega_\Lambda h^2$. The bottom three plots show best-fit values and 3σ ranges of $\Omega_\Lambda h^2$ obtained from Eq. (23) as well as Eq. (22) for both $N_3 = 22$ (cyan vertical band) and $N_3 = 23$ (light pink vertical band). The top two plots depict the values and $3 \times 1\sigma$ ranges of $\Omega_\Lambda h^2$ obtained from DESI [6] and Planck [18] data for $\nu\Lambda$ CDM model.

B. Remarks on QoM Postulate

The QoM postulate does not apply to composite particles like proton. Therefore the mass of a composite particle is not required to be an integer multiple of m_0 .

An immediate consequence of the QoM postulate is that there are no massive particles with mass smaller than m_0 . Any hypothetical massive elementary particle — such as axion, prion, inflaton — must have a mass equal to positive integer multiple of m_0 .

In the QoM postulate, the mass of the lightest neutrino mass eigenstate is assumed to be the smallest quantum of mass (i.e., $m_1 = m_0$). If we relax this requirement and instead assume that the mass of the lightest neutrino mass eigenstate is itself a positive integer multiple of the smallest quantum of mass (i.e., $m_1 = N_1 m_0$ where, N_1 may differ from 1), then we obtain other possibilities for the neutrino masses — for example, $2m_0, 4m_0$ and $20m_0$ (or $21m_0$) with $m_0 = 2.519 \text{ meV}/c^2$ (or $2.398 \text{ meV}/c^2$). Under this scenario, m_0 may represent the mass of a hypothetical elementary particle like axion.

Although the QoM postulate applies to all the elementary particles, we have applied it only in the neutrino sector. Testing its viability for other elementary particles remains an important direction for future investigation.

C. Running Gravitational Coupling Constant

In Quantum Electrodynamics (QED), the value of the fine-structure constant depends on the energy scale, $\alpha(E)$. It is therefore natural to ask whether the gravitational coupling constant α_g may also run with energy scale in a theory of quantum gravity. If α_g does depend on the energy scale, $\alpha_g(E)$, then Eqs. (6), (11) and (13) imply that m_0, ρ_Λ and Λ are also functions of the energy scale.

This possible running of $\alpha_g(E)$ would not necessarily invalidate the Λ CDM model which relies on observations pertaining to the period since the time of photon decoupling at a redshift of $z = 1089.92$. [11] During this period, the energy scale of the universe has changed by only about three orders of magnitude, making it plausible that $\alpha_g(E)$ has remained approximately constant.

However, the running of $\alpha_g(E)$ could have significant implications for the period right after the big bang when the universe was too hot. In particular, a larger early-universe value of $\alpha_g(E)$ may potentially provide a natural explanation for an initial inflationary phase.

D. Conclusion

We have exploited a coincidence between the lightest massive particles, the neutrinos, and the most abundant energy component of the universe, the dark energy, to predict the values of the neutrino masses and the cosmological constant. Observations indicate that the

neutrino masses are of the order $m_i \sim \text{meV}/c^2$ and that the dark energy has a constant density of the order $\rho_\Lambda \sim (\text{meV}/c^2)^4$ (in natural units with $c = \hbar = 1$). With the CC postulate, we formalised this coincidence as a definite relationship between the vacuum energy and the smallest quantum of mass in Eq. (12). By applying the two GCC postulates to neutrino oscillation data, we made multiple testable predictions, including a preference for normal mass ordering, an exact value for the ratio $\frac{\Delta_{31}}{\Delta_{21}}$ and the value of the cosmological constant Λ .

Both the GCC postulates are phenomenological in nature and do not explain the origin of mass quantization or the scaling $\rho_\Lambda \propto m_0^4$. We expect that a complete theory of quantum gravity may provide a deeper justification for these relations and clarify the fundamental role of the gravitational coupling constant α_g .

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